

IMPACT OF MASS MEDIA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH ISSUES: A STUDY OF KADUNA METROPOLIS

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Abstract

This study focuses on “Impact of the Mass Media in the Management of Environmental Health Issues: A Study of Kaduna Metropolis”. The study adopted the Survey design with the questionnaire as instrument of data collection. One hundred questionnaires were administered on respondents, only 78 were properly filled and returned. The study was anchored on two theories: Cultivation and Agenda Setting. The study reveals that the media play a role of sensitizing the people on health matters. The study recommends among other things that the media need to do more on disseminating messages towards disease prevention.

Introduction

The issue of environmental health is undoubtedly one that has generated a lot of debates both locally and internationally. It is a sector or sub-sector that is largely talked about but receiving little or no attention in many places particularly in developing countries.

According to World Health Organization (2005), environmental health is the science that studies the biological, chemical or physical agents introduced into the environment or occurring naturally and their effects on human health and ecological systems. The field also includes the study of human activities, a vital component in our complex ecosystem. In another sense, environmental health is understood as the science of controlling or modifying those conditions, influences, or forces surrounding man which relate to promoting, establishing and maintaining health.

Environmental health as used by the World Health Organization Regional Office for Europe, includes both the direct pathological effects of chemicals, radiation and some biological agents, and the effects (often indirect) on health and wellbeing of the broad physical, psychological, social and aesthetic environment which includes housing, urban development, land use and transport. In general term, environmental health comprises those aspects of human health, including quality of life, that are determined by physical, chemical,

biological, social, and psychosocial factors in the environment. It also refers to the theory and practice of assessing, correcting, controlling, and preventing those factors in the environment that can potentially affect adversely the health of present and future generations. It would be seen from the foregoing that the scope of this field is wide and varied.

The World Health Organization's concept of health brought in focus the ecological as well as the sociological paradigms of health with a view to holistically addressing issues relating to health and wellbeing. If health is seen not just as the absence of disease but also as a central goal of human development, then the protection of the environment and improvement of health are mutually supportive. It is against this background of increasing international focus on environmental sanitation, that the Committee on Environmental Sanitation was established by the first World Health Assembly in 1948. The Committee's first, ground-breaking report, published in 1949, concluded that physical development, health and survival, depended on the management of environmental factors which included excreta and community waste disposal; safe drinking water; food safety; healthy personal habits; understanding the causes of diseases and the control of disease vectors.

Robinson (2001) opines that typical responsibilities of environmental health and protection programs include:

Ambient air quality, Indoor air quality, Water pollution control, Safe drinking water, Noise pollution, Radiation, Food safety, Industrial hygiene, Childhood lead poisoning, Acid deposition, Disaster planning and response, Cross-connection elimination, Healthy housing, Institutional environmental control, Recreational area environmental control, Solid waste management, Vector control, Pesticide control, Toxic chemical control, On-site liquid waste disposal, Unintentional injury control, Bioterrorism and Global environmental issues etc.

The mass media on the other hand, have traditionally been understood to refer to the print channels of mass communication (newspaper, magazines etc), as well as the broadcast channels of mass communication (radio, television etc.). In recent years however, the definition has become broader, as it now encompasses the new media including online journalism, blogging and social media.

From a sociological view Inhonopi and Urim(2011: 9) posits that:

Mass Communication is the methods and organizations used by specialists or social groups to convey messages from a source to large, socially mixed and widely dispersed audiences.

The above definition is important to our understanding of Mass Communication because it highlights key terms like methods, organization, specialists, social groups among others things involved in conveying messages to a socially mixed and dispersed audience. Since this study examines the influence of mass media on environmental health, it is fitting to look at the matter from a sociological point of view. According to Imhonopi and Urim (2011:9)

Sociology of mass communication is simply the objective and systematic analysis or explanation of the structure, processes, techniques or methods of mass communication and its role and influence on the general society.

Mass communication is the process of creating shared meaning between the mass media and their audience, (Baran, 2002). Still, according to Carey (1975) cited in Baran, (2002) communication is a symbolic process

whereby reality is produced, maintained, repaired and transferred. Careys (1975) definition asserts that communication and reality are linked. Communication is a process embedded in our everyday live that inform the way we perceive, understand and construct our view of reality and the world. According to Bitner (1989) mass communication is messages communicated through a mass medium to a large heterogeneous number of people.

According to Wallack (1996), the term “media channel” can generally be seen as tool for the transfer of information, concepts and ideas to both general and specific audience. Using mass media can be counter-productive if the channels used are not audience-appropriate, or if the message being delivered is too emotional, fear-arousing, or controversial. Undesirable side effects usually can be avoided through proper formative research, knowledge of the audience, experience in linking media channels to audiences, and message testing. Marshall McLuhan calls media "extensions of man." That is, the greatest desire of any communicator using any channel is to make sure communication has effect on the receiver. With this, the need for the audience attention is paramount.

Generally speaking, mass media as watchdogs of the society and the Fourth Estate of the Realm rubs on all aspects of societal life, from politics, economy, finance, sports, agriculture, aviation and also health. It is against this background that this study seeks to evaluate the impact of the mass media on management of environmental health issues.

Statement of the problem

Media, comprising newspapers, magazines, bill boards, radio, television, film, internet and even the GSM as well as leaflets are important sources of information and education. In spite of mass media presence in Nigeria, the level of social awareness among people in managing health and environmental issues seems intricate. This is because of the attitudes and behaviours exhibited by people as it concerns environmental sanitation and cleanliness. Water channels are most times blocked with refuse, people pour all sorts of waste materials into water channels during rainfall and even immediate surroundings in residential units most times look unkempt.

Majority of Nigerians lack basic knowledge about their environment and health to take proactive decisions on sanitation matters. This manifests in their traditional environmental sanitation patterns as most people live in unhealthy conditions and treat important issues that are critical to their well-being as trivialities. This research work therefore seeks to determine the impact of the media on environmental health issues. Essentially, to determine how the media influences or can influence positively issues that are pertinent to environment and health.

Therefore, this study is prompted by the need to measure how much the mass media influences the management of environmental health issues, using Kaduna metropolis as the case study.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

- a) Determine the level of media impact on environmental health issues.
- b) Determine the extent to which the mass media created awareness about environmental health.
- c) Determine factors responsible for environmental degradation and unhealthy living.
- d) Determine the level of media influence on people as it concerns their health and environment.
- e) Determine ways people use in managing environmental health issues.

Research Questions

This study seeks to provide answers to the following research questions:

- a) What is the level of media impact on environmental and health issues?
- b) To what extent do the mass media create awareness about environmental health?
- c) What factors are responsible for environmental degradation and unhealthy living?
- d) What is the level of media influence on people as it concerns their health and environment?
- e) What are the ways people adopt in managing environmental health issues?

Literature Review

The Impact of Mass Media in the Management of Environmental Health

The mass media are intensively employed in the management of environmental health. Huge sums are spent annually for materials and salaries and the production and distribution of booklets, pamphlets, newspaper articles, and radio and television programs. These channels are employed at all levels of public health with the hope that three effects might occur: the learning of correct health information and knowledge, the changing of health attitudes and values and the establishment of new health behavior. Mass media campaigns have long been a tool for promoting public health (Noar, 2006) being widely used to expose high proportions of large populations to messages through routine uses of existing media, such as television, radio, and newspapers. Communication campaigns involving diverse topics and target audiences have been conducted for decades.

Exposure to such messages is, therefore, generally passive (Wakefield, 2010). Such campaigns are frequently competing with factors, such as pervasive product marketing, powerful social norms, and behaviors driven by addiction or habit. Mass media campaigns are aimed primarily to change knowledge, awareness and attitudes, contributing to the goal of changing behavior. There has not been a high expectation that such campaigns on their own would change people's behavior.

Scholars suggests that as with other preventive health efforts, mass media campaigns are most likely to reduce unhealthy attitudes if their messages are reinforced by other efforts. Reinforcing factors may include law enforcement efforts, grassroots activities, and other media messages.

There is a vast literature relating to public health information campaigns. Much theoretical literature is devoted to the topic of effectiveness of health communication strategies. Mass media campaigns have usually been one element of broader health promotion programmes with mutually reinforcing components:

- Bringing together partnerships of public, voluntary and private sector bodies and professional organizations.

- Informing and educating the public, but also setting the agenda for public debate about the health topic, thereby modifying the climate of opinion surrounding it.
- Encouraging local and national policy changes so as to create a supportive environment within which people are more able to change their behavior.

The Importance of Communicating Environmental Issues

Certain trends today seem to challenge world leaders as far as environmental problems are concerned. Even the Earth Summits held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, in June 1992 and 2012 have not done much to help the situation. The trends in question have to do with species, fisheries, rainforests, mega-cities, ozone-Layer, Global warming, climate change, transport, nuclear power, war and refugees, as well as the earth's population to mention just a few. These trends have serious implications for Africa in particular, and for the world in general.

First, Africa, already stricken by drought and a host of other environmental problems, could suffer even more. Secondly, the current business as usual scenarios for energy use and population could make it very difficult for homo sapiens (the so-called wise ones) to stay on earth.

Thirdly, environmental damage is irreversible over inestimable number of years. We are incapable of putting lost ozone back into the atmosphere or recreating extinct species. How long would it take to restore soil or tropical rainforest losses.

Fourthly, the trends for many environmental issues such as ozone depletion, acid rain, climate change and rainforest destruction also take decades to identify and reverse. Furthermore, successful action on the most serious environmental threats is more complex without global agreements between the rich and poor countries of the world, a daunting political task requiring strong national action and innovative global diplomacy.

Finally, eco-hazards are often unpredictable - the size of the first measured ozone hole was significantly bigger than scientists had predicted. This means that we must pursue a proactive policy of limiting the impact of

synthetic chemicals and other potential environmental insults, rather than the reactive policy of loading such things into the biosphere and waiting to see what happens. A key condition for a successful proactive policy is the public's right to know about what we are exposing their communities and planet earth to. Such freedom of access to environmental information, communication and data would help to identify early signs of environmental or human harm and to provide the public with a full picture of the implications for environmental pollution of industry's activities. This is where communication of information on environment comes in.

There are several reasons why it is of utmost importance for social scientists, natural scientists, environmentalists, communication researchers, media practitioners, religious leaders, traditional rulers, stakeholders, policy-makers, government functionaries in the legislative, executive and judicial arms of government, farmers, traders and other members of the society including all agencies of socialization to raise public awareness about existing environmental problems. The agencies include the family, the mass media, the schools, and the peer groups etc.

The Role of Communication Media

Laymen and media experts alike agree that the media have a role to play in addressing the ecological crisis facing countries in Africa and elsewhere. They see the mass media as a means of information dissemination for environmental education.

The optimism embedded in the general statements on the role of the media contrasts with the more cautious approach of communication researchers who accompany their affirmation of media roles with warnings about their limitations. The particular target group concerned is a factor in determining the extent of the mass media's effectiveness.

Hansen (1990), for example, cites researchers whose findings show that people who are most active on environmental issues do not often obtain their information from the mass media. Further evidence suggests that media influence on attitudes is greater for key decision makers than it is for the general public.

Hansen also expresses doubt on the ability of the mass media to seriously challenge policy because of their integration into established authorities and the latter's definitions of environmental issues and priority areas. Abraham *et al* (1990) identify a "bandwagon" approach to media coverage of environmental issues which is characterized by motivations deriving from a "competition-driven delivery system" where decisions on media contents are dictated by responsiveness to market demands rather than by concern to generate awareness about a particular issue.

They contrast this with "public education" and "critical public education" approaches, favoring the latter but pointing out that, to be successful, this approach must use forms of media other than news (such as drama and game shows) and be buttressed by the efforts of educational institutions. Lowe and Morrison (1984) observes that the "mass media have fostered rather than undermined environmental protest, and will continue to do so as long as the environment is taken to be a politically neutral area relating to the quality of life rather than its organization."

In India, reasons put forward by one researcher to explain state-owned television's failure to respond effectively to the challenge to educate on controversial aspects of the environment include the low priority accorded the environment, an unwillingness to air controversial programmes on the environment and the Environmental Secretary's lack of aggressive use of television to promote environmental awareness (Ninan, 1990).

Other problems identified by other scholars include the lack of appropriate opportunities and resources to back up media messages with positive environmental measures (Uche, 1990). The remoteness of environmental issues from people's immediate self-interest; and the need to target the audience in a way which is more amenable to interpersonal communication (Anshah, 1991).

Theoretical Framework

Agenda-Setting Theory

In contrast to the extreme views of the direct effects model, the agenda-setting theory of media stated that

mass media determine the issues that concern the public rather than the public's views. Under this theory, the issues that receive the most attention from media become the issues that the public discusses, debates, and demands action on. This means that the media is determining what issues and stories the public thinks about. Therefore, when the media fails to address a particular issue, it becomes marginalized in the minds of the public.

When critics claim that a particular media outlet has an agenda, they are drawing on this theory. Agendas can range from a perceived liberal bias in the news media to the propagation of cutthroat capitalist ethics in films. For example, the agenda-setting theory explains such phenomena as the rise of public opinion against smoking. Before the mass media began taking an antismoking stance, smoking was considered a personal health issue. By promoting antismoking sentiments through advertisements, public relations campaigns, and a variety of media outlets, the mass media moved smoking into the public arena, making it a public health issue rather than a personal health issue (Dearing & Rogers, 1996). More recently, coverage of natural disasters has been prominent in the news. However, as news coverage wanes, so does the general public's interest.

Research Design

Research design is the plan, structure of investigation conceived so as to obtain answers to research questions and to control variance (Kerlinger, 1973; Kotari, 2010): It serves as the blue print that aids the researcher to come-up with solutions to identified problems and guide him or her in various stages of the research.

Some social scientists states that there are two types of research designs. It is often identified with survey research, a method of data collection common in many social science studies.

The main advantage of this is to permit the researcher to employ samples which allow the researchers to make statistical inference to generalize their findings to real life situation, thereby increasing the external validity of the study. A well articulated design is desirable

because it serves as veritable guide for the generation of primary data.

Survey design involves the planning of the whole study and outlining the steps to take when conducting the survey. These steps start from the formulation of the survey goals and end at the interpretation of the survey results.

Sample

One Hundred respondents were selected from the study population as the sample of the study. The sample consists of both male and female respondents.

Method of Data Collection

Data in this study were collected by field survey to obtain responses through the use of the instrument of questionnaire. The questionnaires were administered by the researcher. Respondents were restricted to options and were asked to tick only the right answers. The questionnaire contain questions derived from the objectives and research questions.

In this way, relevant demographic information on the respondents were collected as well as other variables relevant for the study. Copies of these questionnaires were administered on the sampled populatio by the researcher.

Data Analysis /Procedure

The choice of the method of analysis depended on the scale of measurement adopted during collection process. Data analysis is a practice in which raw data is ordered and organized so that useful information can be extracted from it. Gall and Borg (2007) states that quantitative data are analyzed using descriptive statistics. This means data collected are presented and analyzed using simple frequency tables and simple percentages.

Data Presentation

The analyzed data were presented in a tabulated form, with the tables showing frequencies and percentages as collated. One hundred (100) questionnaires were administered to respondents but seventy-eight (78) were retrieved, as twelve (12) were either invalid or not returned. Therefore, the data analyzed were based on 78 returned and valid questionnaires.

Table 1: Media Campaign on Health

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	65	83
No	13	17
Total	78	100%

Field survey, July 2018

The above table shows that 65 respondents representing 83% have experienced a media campaign on health while 13 respondents representing 17% % have not experienced a media campaign on health. This means that majority of the respondents have experienced a media campaign on health.

Table 2: Media Campaign on various Health issues

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Immunization awareness campaign	40	51
Ante & Post-natal awareness campaign	38	49
Total	78	100%

Field survey, July 2018

The above table shows that 40 respondents representing 51% have experienced a media campaign on health focusing on immunization awareness while 38 respondents representing 49% have experienced a media campaign on health focusing on Ante and Post-natal awareness campaign. This indicates that majority of the respondents have experienced a media campaign on health focusing on immunization awareness.

Table 3: Access to media campaigns on Health

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	45	58
No	33	42
Total	78	100%

Field survey, July 2018

The above table shows that 45 respondents representing 58% agree that members of the society have time to access radio/TV campaigns on health while 33 respondents representing 42% do not agree that members of the society have time to access radio/TV campaigns on health. This shows that majority of the respondents agree that members of the society have time to access radio/TV campaigns on health.

Table 4: Media’s role in sensitization on health

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	71	91
No	7	9
Total	78	100%

Field survey, July 2018

The above table shows that 71 respondents representing 91% agree that the media has a role to play in sensitizing people on the importance of health while 7 respondents representing 9% do not agree that the media has a role to play in sensitizing people on the importance of health. This shows that majority of the respondents agree that the media has a role to play in sensitizing people on the importance of health.

Table 5: Role of Traditional Rulers on Improving media sensitization

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Role of traditional rulers	21	27
Government financial support	57	73
Total	78	100%

Field survey, July 2018

The above table indicates that 21 respondents representing 27% are of the opinion that traditional rulers have a role to play in improving sensitization through TV/Radio campaigns while 57 respondents representing 73% opine that Government financial support is what is needed to improve sensitization through TV/Radio campaigns. This shows that majority of the respondents agree Government financial support is needed to improve sensitization through radio/TV campaign.

Table 6: Health Media campaign influence on society

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	62	79
No	16	21
Total	78	100%

Field survey, July 2018

The above table shows that 62 respondents representing 79% agree that the society is influenced by media campaign on health issues while 16 respondents representing 21% do not agree that the society is influenced by media campaign on health issues. This indicates that majority of the respondents agree that the society is influenced by media campaign on health issues.

Table 7: Media effectiveness in promoting policies

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	69	88
No	9	12
Total	78	100%

Field survey, July 2018

The table above shows that 69 respondents representing 88% agree that the media is effective in promoting government policies and interest towards members of the society while 9 of the respondents representing 12% do not agree that the media is effective in promoting government policies and interest towards members of the society. This shows that majority of the respondents agree that the media is effective in promoting government policies and interest towards members of the society.

Table 8: Achievement of media campaigns in Kaduna metropolis

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	45	58
No	33	42
Total	78	100%

Field survey, July 2018

The above table shows that 45 respondents representing 58% agree that achievement has been made in media campaigns in Kaduna while 33 respondents representing 42% do not agree that achievement has been made in media campaigns in Kaduna . This shows that majority of the respondents agree that a significant achievement

has been made in media campaigns in Kaduna metropolis.

Table 9: Other organizations involved in sensitization campaign.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	66	85
No	12	15
Total	78	100%

Field survey, July 2018

The above table shows that 66 respondents representing 85% agree that there are other organizations involved in sensitization campaigns while 12 respondents representing 15% do not agree that there are other organizations involved in sensitization campaigns. This shows that majority of the respondents agree that there are other organizations involved in sensitization campaigns.

Table 10: Reason why Government is unwilling to commit to sensitization

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Huge amount involved	43	55
Inability to reach target population	35	45
Total	78	100%

Field survey, July 2018

The above table shows that 43 respondents representing 55% believe that huge amount involved in media campaigns and sensitization was the reason behind government’s unwillingness to use the mass media while 35 respondents representing 45% believe that inability of media campaign to reach target audience was the reason behind government’s unwillingness to use the mass media. This shows that majority of the population believed that huge amount involved in media campaigns and sensitization was the reason behind government’s unwillingness to use the mass media.

Conclusion

The media has been described as the Fourth Estate of the Realm, this is in recognition of its important roles such as Surveillance, Agenda-Setting, correlation, Mobilization, Sensitization etc. In the course of this study, respondents agreed that media has a role to play

in sensitizing people on health matters. In partnership with health-related agencies and NGOs, mass media organizations must train and re-train health reporters to be up-to-date with trends, understand health and medical jargons. This will advertently help for better reportage and coverage of health issues, and environmental health in particular.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made:

Firstly, Nigerian media practitioners should put more efforts on information gathering and dissemination on diseases towards presenting and controlling diseases using the mass media as a means of teaching, enlightening and influencing people at all levels.

Secondly, the government and Non-Governmental Organizations, private individuals and even other health bodies should help in fighting diseases and thereby improving our health, for one cannot over-emphasize the importance of joint efforts in effective control and prevention of diseases.

Thirdly, the media practitioners should use local languages or dialects appropriate for their target audiences to understand health messages. Members of the press should be trained adequately to make effective use of the press on eliminating and reducing disease spread.

Fourthly, there should be regular press conferences by the Ministry of Health for the press to be able to communicate accurately balance and factual information.

Fifthly, Mass Communication students in all higher institutions in Nigeria should be trained extensively on health issues to enable them report effectively on environmental health issues

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